

Sustainable Development for Ensuring Healthy Lives and Promoting Well-Being on Earth through Yoga Education-With Special Reference to India's Contribution to The World

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Abstract

Health has a central place in SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages, underpinned by 13 targets that cover a wide spectrum of WHO's work. Ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being at all ages is essential to sustainable development. Before the pandemic, major progress was made in improving the health of millions of people. By the end of 2021, the situation had improved somewhat, but many people remain unable to get the care and support they need for both pre-existing and new mental health conditions. Even before the pandemic, depression, anxiety and other mental health challenges affected far too many children. Transform the world aiming at individual human beings. There is need to change the way an individual perceive, experience, think, feel and act in this world to change the world. This research paper is based on the secondary data sourced from journals, magazines, articles and published reports of UNESCO and other agencies. The objective of the study is to study the contribution of Yoga education in maintaining mental health and wellness of individual for achieving future sustainable development Goal and to analyse the performance and status of India with respect to SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages. It was found that Yoga has proven beneficial in treating mental illnesses such as post-traumatic stress disorders and generalized anxiety disorders. Yoga education can supplement transforming Individual. It can prepare individual physically and mentally for the integration of their physical, mental and spiritual faculties so that they can become healthier, saner and more integrated members of the society and of the nation. India has given the best gift to the world through "Yoga". United Nations General Assembly resolution 69/131 endorsed by a record 175 countries in December 2014, proclaimed 21 June as the International Day of Yoga as India worked on it for years to happen and was admired by the world too. It is also discovered that Yoga / Ayurveda / Wellness is being promoted in the past years in the print, electronic, internet and outdoor medium under the Ministry of Tourism's "Incredible India Campaign and promoted the Wellness Tourism by also instituted a National Tourism Award for the category of "Best Wellness Centre". It is suggested that Yoga is a powerful tool for individuals, communities and countries to improve not only physical but also mental health, and to prevent and control non communicable diseases (NCDs). Schools, workplaces, civil society organizations and communities should consider incorporating yoga into daily activities, and adopt yoga to promote health, prevent and manage diseases.

Keywords: Yoga education, Mental Health & Wellness, Sustainable development.

Introduction:

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are 17 goals with 169 targets that all 191 UN Member States have agreed to try to achieve by the year 2030. Health has a central place in SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages, underpinned by 13 targets that cover a wide spectrum of WHO's work. Almost all of the other 16 goals are directly related to health or will contribute to health indirectly¹.

Ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being at all ages is essential to sustainable development. The world faced a global health crisis i.e. COVID-19 which led to spreading

human suffering, destabilizing the global economy and upending the lives of billions of people around the globe. Health emergencies such as COVID-19 pose a global risk and have shown the critical need for preparedness. By focusing on providing more efficient funding of health systems, improved sanitation and hygiene, and increased access to physicians, significant progress can be made in helping to save the lives of millions². By the end of 2021, the situation had improved somewhat, but many people remain unable to get the care and support they need for both pre-existing and new mental health conditions. Even before the pandemic, depression, anxiety and other mental health

challenges affected far too many children. It is estimated that, in 2019, more than 13 per

cent of adolescents aged 10 to 19 had a diagnosed mental disorder as defined by the WHO; this translates into 86 million adolescents aged 15 to 19 and 80 million adolescents aged 10 to 14. The pandemic has added to the mental health issues facing children and young people, since many of them are still experiencing school closures, disruption of daily routines, and stress over food insecurity and loss of family income, and uncertainty about the future³.

“Sustainable Development Goals” addressing human wellbeing as seventeen different issues which are concerned with poverty, nourishment, health, women’s issues, environment, etc. This is the effort that has been going on in the world for a long time. Transform the world aiming at individual human beings. There is need to change the way an individual perceive, experience, think, feel and act in this world to change the world. Spending money in projects will not only work alone rather concentration should be done to transform human beings on a large scale then only there will be a true transformation in the world⁴.

Yoga education can supplement transforming Individual. It can prepare individual physically and mentally for the integration of their physical, mental and spiritual faculties so that they can become healthier, saner and more integrated members of the society and of the nation. Yoga education helps in self-discipline and self-control, leading to immense amount of awareness, concentration and higher level of consciousness. The aims and objectives of Yoga education are -to enable the individual to have good health; to practice mental hygiene; to possess emotional stability; to integrate moral values and to attain higher level of consciousness⁵.

Yoga in Sanskrit means ‘union’, which can refer to the union between the mind, body and soul; but also to the union between the individual consciousness and the universal consciousness in a much broader sense. As a practice, yoga is not only good for exercising and stretching the body – it also has a lot of psychological as well as spiritual benefits, training the mind to observe and create an awareness of its own nature. Furthermore, it fosters a sense of harmony between the body,

the mind and the surrounding environment, which in turn promotes conscious actions and

behaviour towards other humans, nature and our planet Earth⁶.

Yoga Sutras, a treatise on the theory and practice of yoga, is attributed to *Patanjali*, a notable scholar in ancient India, who lived over 2000 years ago. He laid out an eight-fold path to yoga which put forward a code of conduct for individuals. Out of these so-called eight “limbs” of yoga, three are better known than others. These are *asanas* (physical postures), *pranayama* (breathing exercises) and *dhyana* (meditation). The remaining five are less well-known. These are *yamas* (ethical restraints), *niyamas* (ethical observances), *pratyahara* (withdrawal of senses), *dharana* (concentration) and *samadhi* (super consciousness). Collectively, these limbs attribute to the spiritual practice of yoga and can potentially have a transcendental effect on the practitioner. The withdrawal of senses, concentration and super consciousness are to do with the spiritual aspirations, while the ethical restraints and ethical observances are to do with everyday actions. These are most relevant to addressing the global challenges and achieving the SDGs. Yoga has proven beneficial in treating mental illnesses such as post-traumatic stress disorders and generalized anxiety disorders⁷.

Review of literature:

Meagan L. Weisner & Mary M. Cameron (2020)⁸, This study aims to increase understanding of whether spiritual dimensions of nature experiences are connected to sustainability by examining the relationship between yoga, sensory awareness, and pro-environmental behaviour among comparative groups of yoga and non-yoga practitioners in South Florida. According to affective and perceptual theories of human environmental care, the heightened perception of and attention to one’s natural environment through enhanced sensory awareness that yoga practitioners describe experiencing should engender a closer inclination to nature and its protection, as measured by pro-environmental acts. South Florida yoga practitioners describe increased sensory awareness after yoga, yet they practiced common natural resources protective actions like recycling and reducing

fossil fuel use no more frequently than their non-yoga counterparts.

Sharma Chander & Amrita Sharma (2020)⁹, Yoga and meditation are believed to start with the very inception of civilization and have munificent effects physically as well as mentally. As the entire world is facing dreadful COVID-19 pandemic, the concept of Yoga and meditation is the best way to keep a person in good shape, physically and mentally. Yoga along with meditation, as an integral part of our lifestyle tells us how to control the basic thought process and to stabilize oneself and integrate the state of health. Keeping the COVID-19 pandemic in mind, it is time for us to look back to utilize the treasure of Yoga and meditation for immunity, strengthening our willpower to stand the challenges of pandemic and develop resilience against negativity. Yoga usually emphasizes Asana, Pranayama, Dhyana and if practiced on daily basis will increase endorphins-feel-good-chemicals within the body and reduces cortisol levels that cause stress. It was suggested that pandemic has shown worldwide devastating effects on health-care-system, so Yoga and meditation practices could be utilized to counter the negatives of individual's physical, emotional as well as social health.

Aglaia Zafeiroudi & Mathildi Pipinia (2021)¹⁰, Yoga philosophy includes ethical codes of conduct, guidelines, meditation and other practices that respect the Earth, its natural resources, humans and other living beings. The purpose of the present study was to investigate the effects of yoga practice on practitioners' environmental behaviours and sustainability. A total of 195 adults (66 men and 129 women) from two cities in Greece participated in this study. The participants completed the General Environmental Responsible Behaviour scale (Zafeiroudi & Hatzigeorgiadis, 2013) and provided additional information about their personal lifestyles, leisure activity preferences and frequency of participation in outdoor activities. Independent sample T-test analysis was used to investigate differences between practitioners' demographics and the General Environmental Responsible Behaviour scale as the dependent variable. The results indicated statistically significant differences in environmental behaviour

scores among practitioners in different yoga demographics. On the basis of yoga philosophy, the study findings suggested that

participation in yoga practices strengthens beliefs, behaviours and awareness regarding the environment. The individual values taught by the philosophy of yoga also foster friendlier attitudes and behaviours towards the environment.

HR Dayananda Swamy & Govindasamy Agoramoorthy (2022)¹¹, this study discusses the less known aspect of how students can learn more about yoga-based knowledge to refine their personalities to promote the SDGs. It also discusses teachers, especially those who lead yoga knowledge transferring enterprises in catalysing the active participation of learners leading to sustainable outcomes to preserve nature and decelerate climate change consequences. It was found that Learning based on indigenous knowledge has been widely accepted as an important means to inspire and enforce the sustainable development goals (SDGs) mandated by the United Nations. Nevertheless, little is known on the potential of yoga-based traditional learning to enhance the SDGs. In fact, yoga-based learning started in India over two millennia ago, and the practice has gained global attention in recent decades. Enhancing the sustainable development goals through yoga-based learning.

Research Methodology: This research paper is based on the secondary data sourced from journals, magazines, articles and published reports. Different aspects of need of Yoga education for mental health and wellness leads to Sustainable development and India's contribution towards the SDG -3 are studied in the light of reports by different agencies.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the contribution of Yoga education in maintaining mental health and wellness of individual for achieving future sustainable development Goal.
2. To analyse the performance and status of India with respect to SDG 3: Ensure healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages.

India's Contribution to the World:

India has given the best gift to the world through “Yoga”. As we progress in technology and sciences, the balance between human beings and nature needs to be balanced sustainably. The physical and mental well-being of humans will work to support nature to flourish and grow. The calmness we are finding outside is within us that we need to realize which is only possible with the help of Yoga. Every year India celebrate International Yoga Day on 21st June United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals aim at sustainable health and environment-friendly health practices. United Nations General Assembly resolution 69/131 endorsed by a record 175 countries in December 2014, proclaimed 21 June as the International Day of Yoga as India worked on it for years to happen and was admired by the world too¹².

Global momentum is growing, and is being led by our Region. In March, WHO and the Government of India signed an agreement to establish the WHO Global Centre for Traditional Medicine (GCTM) in Jamnagar, India. The GCTM – which is supported by an investment of USD 250 million from the Government of India – has a strategic focus on evidence and learning, data and analytics, sustainability and equity, and innovation and technology, with the overall aim of optimizing the contribution of traditional medicine (TRM) to global health and sustainable development. It will significantly contribute to Regional and global efforts to leverage safe, effective and evidence-based TRM to help achieve universal health coverage (UHC), the Flagship Priority and SDG target that underpins all others¹³.

India today also has immense facilities and enormous scope of healthcare wellness tourism including Ayurveda, alternative and holistic treatment. India is perceived worldwide, as one of the true spiritual homes of the modern wellness movement and has a powerful and unique ‘wellness halo’ with its ancient, rich history of Ayurveda, yoga and meditation. India is attracting tourists seeking serenity and optimum health and is emerging as one of the fastest-growing wellness market in the world and a thought-leader in the travel category of wellness tourism. India’s 1st healthcare tourism portal, <http://www.indiahealthcaretourism.com>,

launched by Government of India has complete information about hospitals as well as wellness centres providing Ayurvedic and alternative holistic treatment¹⁵.

India is the most popular tourist destination in South Asia, and it is rapidly expanding. In 2019, the country welcomed almost 18 million international tourists, up from 17.42 million in 2018 while it decreased to only 6.33 million in 2020. India is one of the most preferred destinations for wellness tourism with more than 48.2 million wellness trips in 2020. Before the pandemic, India was the fastest-growing market for wellness tourism. Various places like Kerala and Uttarkhand are being developed as a special place for wellness tourism. Kerala is considered an authentic and place-based wellness tourism centre for Ayurveda. Similarly, Uttarkhand is renowned for its Yoga Study Centre in Rishikesh which also got featured in Trip advisors Top 10 wellness destination. With 48.2 million trips in 2020, India was in the 12th position of 20 preferred destinations for wellness tourism. The total wellness expenditure for India was USD 11.4 billion in 2017 while it decreased to USD 7.2 billion in 2020 due to pandemic. The wellness tourism expenditure decreased by almost half for the year 2020. However, the market is expected to experience increased expenditure in the wellness tourism market with an increase in the number of tourist inflow post pandemic¹⁶. In order to provide dedicated institutional framework to take forward the cause of promotion of Medical Tourism, Wellness Tourism and Yoga, Ayurveda Tourism and any other format of Indian system of medicine covered by Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha and Homeopathy (AYUSH), Ministry has constituted a National Medical & Wellness Tourism Board with the Hon’ble Minister (Tourism) as its Chairman. The Board works as umbrella organization that promotes this segment of tourism in an organized manner. Yoga / Ayurveda / Wellness is being promoted in the past years in the print, electronic, internet and outdoor medium under the Ministry of Tourism’s “Incredible India Campaign”. In order to promote the Wellness Tourism in the country, the Ministry of Tourism has also instituted a National Tourism Award for the Category of “Best Wellness Centre”¹⁷.

Out of the \$5 trillion wellness market, India will contribute around 3-4 per cent by 2025. This is a huge jump from the total contribution of less than 0.25 per cent of the total global market. An average Indian millennial now spends INR 4,000 per month on fitness and wellness. This spending will rise in terms of ticket size and the number of people in this bracket¹⁸.

Suggestions:

The theme of this year's International Day of Yoga is "Yoga for humanity" – a theme both fitting and timely. Yoga is beneficial for people of all ages and incomes. It can be practiced anywhere, at any time, and by people of all countries and cultures¹⁹. Yoga is a powerful tool for individuals, communities and countries to improve not only physical but also mental health, and to prevent and control non communicable diseases (NCDs) – one of the WHO South-East Asia Region's eight Flagship Priorities. Schools, workplaces, civil society organizations and communities should consider incorporating yoga into daily activities, supporting each country's mission to achieve a 15% relative reduction in physical inactivity by 2030 – the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target. Where appropriate, health care providers should encourage patients to adopt yoga to promote health, prevent and manage diseases -- including NCDs – and accelerate recovery from ill-health and injuries²⁰.

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